

Solutions with Cylindrical Symmetry for Graviton Field in Linear Approximation: The Gauge Degrees of Freedom

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The theory of the graviton field in linear approximation is studied. We apply the matrix equation in Minkowski space-time, specifying it the cylindrical coordinates t, r, ϕ, z and tetrad. By diagonalizing the operators of the energy, the third projection of the total angular momentum, and the third projection of the linear momentum, we derive the system of 39 differential equations in polar coordinate r . It is resolved with the use of the method by Fedorov–Gronskiy. In accordance with this, dependance of all 39 functions is determined through only five different functions of the variable r , in the case under consideration they are expressed in terms of Bessel functions. We have constructed six linearly independent solutions of the basic equation. In order to eliminate the gauge degrees of freedom, we use the general definition for gauge solutions according to the Pauli–Fierz approach, now adjusted to tetrad formalism. These gauge solutions are constructed with the use the exact solutions for massless spin 1 field. In this way, we find explicit form of four independent gauge solutions for spin 2 field. In the end, we find a explicit form of two gauge-free solutions for spin 2 field, as it should be expected by physical reason.

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1. Introduction

After the study by Pauli and Fierz [11],[22], the theory of massive and massless fields with spin 2 has always attracted much attention [3]–[28]. Mostly, the studies were performed in the framework of 2-nd order equations. However, it is known that many specific difficulties may be avoided if from the very beginning we start with 1st order equations. The first systematic study for the theory of spin 2 fields within the 1st order formalism performed by F.I. Fedorov [6]. This approach requires a field function with 39 tensor components. This theory was re-discovered and improved by Regee [8]. The approach developed in [6] was based on the general theory of relativistic wave equations elaborated by Gel'fand and Yaglom [4].

In the present paper we develop the theory of the massless spin 2 particle within the tetrad formalism by Tetrode – Weyl – Fock – Ivanenko (for more detaion see in [27]). We apply the matrix equation in Minkowski space-time, specifying it in cylindrical coordinates t, r, ϕ, z and tetrad. By diagonalizing the operators of

the energy, the third projection of the total angular momentum, and the third projection of the linear momentum, we derive the system of 39 differential equations in the polar coordinate r . In order to resolve this system, we apply the method by Fedorov – Gronskiy [10] based on the projective operator method. In accordance with this method, dependance of all 39 functions is determined by only five different functions of the polar variable r , which in the case under consideration are expressed in terms of Bessel functions. We find in explicit form six linearly independent solutions of the basic matrix equation. In order to eliminate the gauge degrees of freedom, we use the general structure of the gauge solutions according to Pauli – Fierz approach, now specified for cylindrical coordinates and tetra. Such gauge solutions are constructed on the base of exact solutions for a massless spin 1 field (in terms of the Bessel functions as well). In this way, we find explicit form of four independent gauge solutions for spin 2 field. In the end, we derive explicit form of two gauge-free solutions for spin 2 field.

2. The basic system of equations and method by Fedorov – Gronskiy

Let us start with the system of differential equations for the massless spin 2 particle in cylindrical coordinates (we use results obtained in [29] for massive spin 2 particle, but now specified for the massless case, so the scalar component of the complete field function equals zero). First we write down the first equation related to the scalar field:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 - i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 - ikh_2\varphi_1 = 0 \tag{2.1}$$

Remaining equations are collected in five groups (we preserve notations from [29])

$\underline{V_1, S_1, P_1}$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 + 2ikd_2\varphi_1 + 2i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 = 6h_0\varphi_1, \\ & \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 + 2i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 + 2ikf_2\varphi_1 = 6h_2\varphi_1, \\ & 3\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 + 3\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 \\ & \quad + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 + 2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 \\ & -2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 6i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 - 4i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 + 2ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 12ikh_2\varphi_1 = 0, \\ & \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 \\ & \quad + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 - 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 \\
 & -2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 + 4i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 - 2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 - 2ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_2\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{10}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{30}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{32}\varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{12}\varphi_2 \\
 & + 2ikE_{22}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_0\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{20}\varphi_1 - 4i\epsilon h_2\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{12}\varphi_3 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{21}\varphi_2 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+1}B_{23}\varphi_3 \\
 & + \sqrt{2}b_{m-1}B_{32}\varphi_2 - 3\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}E_{10}\varphi_2 + 3\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}E_{30}\varphi_3 \\
 & - 2\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}h_1\varphi_2 + 2\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}h_3\varphi_3 \\
 & + 2i\epsilon E_{13}\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{22}\varphi_1 + 2i\epsilon E_{31}\varphi_1 - 12i\epsilon h_0\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{11}\varphi_1 - 2ikB_{33}\varphi_1 + 6ikE_{20}\varphi_1 + 4ikh_2\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 - ikf_0\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 - E_{20}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 - ikc_2\varphi_1 + B_{11}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 + i\epsilon c_2\varphi_1 + E_{31}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 - i\epsilon c_2\varphi_1 - E_{13}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0\varphi_1 + i\epsilon f_2\varphi_1 + \frac{2}{3}ikd_2\varphi_1 + E_{22}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikf_2\varphi_1 + ikc_2\varphi_1 + B_{33}\varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}c_1\varphi_3 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}c_3\varphi_2 - B_{22}\varphi_1 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m-1}d_1\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m+1}d_3\varphi_3 - B_{20}\varphi_1 = 0;
 \end{aligned}$$

V_2, S_2, P_2

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sqrt{2}a_m c_2\varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-2}f_1\varphi_4 + 2ikc_3\varphi_2 + 2i\epsilon d_1\varphi_2 = 6h_1\varphi_2, \\
 & \sqrt{2}a_m B_{11}\varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}a_m B_{22}\varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}b_{m-2}B_{31}\varphi_4 - 2\sqrt{2}a_m h_2\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{12}\varphi_2 - 2i\epsilon E_{21}\varphi_2 + 2ikB_{32}\varphi_2 + 4ikh_1\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & -\sqrt{2}a_m B_{20}\varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_{m-2}E_{11}\varphi_4 + \sqrt{2}a_m E_{31}\varphi_1 - 2\sqrt{2}a_m h_0\varphi_1 + 2ikB_{30}\varphi_2 + 2ikE_{21}\varphi_2 - 2i\epsilon E_{10}\varphi_2 - 4i\epsilon h_1\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-2}f_1\varphi_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_m c_2\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m f_0\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_3\varphi_2 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_1\varphi_2 + E_{10}\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_{m-2}f_1\varphi_4 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_m c_2\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m f_2\varphi_1 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_3\varphi_2 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1\varphi_2 + B_{32}\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}a_m c_2\varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}b_{m-2}f_1\varphi_4 + \frac{1}{3}ikc_3\varphi_2 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1\varphi_2 - B_{21}\varphi_2 = 0, \\
 & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m d_2\varphi_1 - i\epsilon c_3\varphi_2 - ME_{12}\varphi_2 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_m d_2\varphi_1 + ikd_1\varphi_2 + B_{30}\varphi_2 = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_3\varphi_2 + ikd_1\varphi_2 + E_{21}\varphi_2 = 0;
 \end{aligned}$$

V_3, S_3, P_3

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\sqrt{2}b_m c_2\varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+2}f_3\varphi_5 + 2ikc_1\varphi_3 + 2i\epsilon d_3\varphi_3 = 6h_3\varphi_3, \\
 & \sqrt{2}a_{m+2}B_{13}\varphi_5 - \sqrt{2}b_m B_{22}\varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}b_m B_{33}\varphi_1 + 2\sqrt{2}b_m h_2\varphi_1 - 2i\epsilon E_{23}\varphi_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{32}\varphi_3 - 2ikB_{12}\varphi_3 + 4ikh_3\varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & -\sqrt{2}b_m B_{20}\varphi_1 - \sqrt{2}b_m E_{13}\varphi_1 + \sqrt{2}a_{m+2}E_{33}\varphi_5 + 2\sqrt{2}b_m h_0\varphi_1 - 2ikB_{10}\varphi_3 + 2ikE_{23}\varphi_3 - 2i\epsilon E_{30}\varphi_3 - 4i\epsilon h_3\varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_m c_2\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+2}f_3\varphi_5 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m f_0\varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1\varphi_3 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_3\varphi_3 + E_{30}\varphi_3 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m f_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{2}{3}ikc_1 \varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 \varphi_3 - B_{12} \varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}b_m c_2 \varphi_1 + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}a_{m+2} f_3 \varphi_5 - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 \varphi_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 \varphi_3 - B_{23} \varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m d_2 \varphi_1 - ikd_3 \varphi_3 + B_{10} \varphi_3 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_m d_2 \varphi_1 + i\epsilon c_1 \varphi_3 + E_{32} \varphi_3 = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_1 \varphi_3 + ikd_3 \varphi_3 + E_{23} \varphi_3 = 0; \\
 & \underline{V_4, S_4, P_4} \\
 & a_{m-1} B_{21} \varphi_2 + 2a_{m-1} h_1 \varphi_2 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{31} \varphi_4 + \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{11} \varphi_4 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1} d_1 \varphi_2 - i\epsilon f_1 \varphi_4 - E_{11} \varphi_4 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}a_{m-1} c_3 \varphi_2 + ikf_1 \varphi_4 + B_{31} \varphi_4 = 0; \\
 & \underline{V_5, S_5, P_5} \\
 & -b_{m+1} B_{23} \varphi_3 + 2b_{m+1} h_3 \varphi_3 - \sqrt{2}ikB_{13} \varphi_5 - \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{33} \varphi_5 = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1} d_3 \varphi_3 + i\epsilon f_3 \varphi_5 + E_{33} \varphi_5 = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}b_{m+1} c_1 \varphi_3 - ikf_3 \varphi_5 + B_{13} \varphi_5 = 0,
 \end{aligned}$$

where short notations for differential operators are used

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_m &= \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m}{r}, \quad a_{m+2} = \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m+2}{r}, \quad a_{m+1} = \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m+1}{r}, \quad a_{m-1} = \frac{d}{dr} + \frac{m-1}{r}, \\
 b_m &= \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m}{r}, \quad b_{m-2} = \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m-2}{r}, \quad b_{m+1} = \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m+1}{r}, \quad b_{m-1} = \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m-1}{r}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.2}$$

According to Fedorov – Gronskiy method [10], the above system should be consistent with the following differential constraints

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_{m-1} \varphi_2 &= C_1 \varphi_1, \quad a_m \varphi_1 = C_3 \varphi_2; \quad a_{m+1} \varphi_3 = C_2 \varphi_1, \quad b_m \varphi_1 = C_5 \varphi_3; \\
 b_{m-2} \varphi_4 &= C_4 \varphi_2, \quad a_{m-1} \varphi_2 = C_7 \varphi_4; \quad a_{m+2} \varphi_5 = C_6 \varphi_3, \quad b_{m+1} \varphi_3 = C_8 \varphi_5;
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.3}$$

therefore, taking in mind eq. (2.1), we should set $h_1 \equiv 0, h_3 \equiv 0$.

These relations permit us to transform the above system to algebraic form (see below); besides they permit to derive second order equations for separate functions:

$$\begin{aligned}
 (b_{m-1} a_m - C_1 C_3) \varphi_1 &= 0, & (a_m b_{m-1} - C_1 C_3) \varphi_2 &= 0; \\
 (a_{m+1} b_m - C_2 C_5) \varphi_1 &= 0, & (b_m a_{m+1} - C_2 C_5) \varphi_3 &= 0; \\
 (b_{m-2} a_{m-1} - C_4 C_7) \varphi_2 &= 0, & (a_{m-1} b_{m-2} - C_4 C_7) \varphi_4 &= 0; \\
 (a_{m+2} b_{m+1} - C_6 C_8) \varphi_3 &= 0, & (b_{m+1} a_{m+2} - C_6 C_8) \varphi_5 &= 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.4}$$

It is evident that we can assume identities $C_3 = C_1, C_5 = C_2, C_7 = C_4, C_8 = C_6$. Equations for five basic functions $\varphi_i(r)$ read (where $X = C_3^2 = C_5^2 = C_7^2 = C_8^2 = C^2$)

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{m^2}{r^2} - X \right] \varphi_1 = 0, \\
 & \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{(m-1)^2}{r^2} - X \right] \varphi_2 = 0, \quad \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{(m+1)^2}{r^2} - X \right] \varphi_3 = 0, \\
 & \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{(m-2)^2}{r^2} - X \right] \varphi_4 = 0, \quad \left[\frac{d^2}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} - \frac{(m+2)^2}{r^2} - X \right] \varphi_5 = 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.5}$$

Solutions of these equations should be in agree with the gauge solutions, which are expressed in terms of Bessel functions of the argument $z = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} r$ (see below), in equations (2.5) we should set $X = -(\epsilon^2 - k^2)$. In this way, instead of (2.5) we get equations of Bessel type in the variable $z = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} r$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} + 1 - \frac{m^2}{z^2} \right] \varphi_1 = 0, \quad \varphi_1(z) = L_1 J_{\pm m}(z); \\ & \left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} + 1 - \frac{(m-1)^2}{z^2} \right] \varphi_2 = 0, \quad \varphi_2(z) = L_2 J_{\pm(m-1)}(z); \\ & \left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} + 1 - \frac{(m+1)^2}{z^2} \right] \varphi_3 = 0, \quad \varphi_3(z) = L_3 J_{\pm(m+1)}(z); \\ & \left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} + 1 - \frac{(m-2)^2}{z^2} \right] \varphi_4 = 0, \quad \varphi_4(z) = L_4 J_{\pm(m-2)}(z); \\ & \left[\frac{d^2}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{z} \frac{d}{dz} + 1 - \frac{(m+2)^2}{z^2} \right] \varphi_5 = 0, \quad \varphi_5(z) = L_5 J_{\pm(m+2)}(z). \end{aligned} \tag{2.6}$$

Further, in the resulting algebraic system we set $C = i\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} = W$; so it has the form

$$-i\epsilon h_0 - ikh_2 = 0, \quad h_1 = 0, \quad h_3 = 0;$$

V_1, S_1, P_1

$$\begin{aligned} & -\sqrt{2}d_1W + \sqrt{2}d_3W + 2ikd_2 + 2i\epsilon f_0 = 6h_0, \quad \sqrt{2}c_1W - \sqrt{2}c_3W + 2i\epsilon d_2 + 2ikf_2 = 6h_2; \\ & 3\sqrt{2}B_{12}W - \sqrt{2}B_{21}W - \sqrt{2}B_{23}W + 3\sqrt{2}B_{32}W - \sqrt{2}E_{10}W + \sqrt{2}E_{30}W + 2\sqrt{2}h_1W - 2\sqrt{2}h_3W \\ & \quad - 2ikB_{11} - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 6i\epsilon E_{22} - 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 4i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{33} + 2ikE_{20} + 12ikh_2 = 0, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{12}W - \sqrt{2}B_{21}W - \sqrt{2}B_{23}W + \sqrt{2}B_{32}W + \sqrt{2}E_{10}W - \sqrt{2}E_{30}W + 2\sqrt{2}h_1W - 2\sqrt{2}h_3W \\ & \quad - 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} - 2i\epsilon E_{31} + 4i\epsilon h_0 - 2ikB_{11} + 2ikB_{33} - 2ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 0, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{10}W + \sqrt{2}B_{30}W + \sqrt{2}E_{32}W - \sqrt{2}E_{12}W + 2ikE_{22} + 4ikh_0 - 2i\epsilon E_{20} - 4i\epsilon h_2 = 0, \\ & \sqrt{2}B_{12}W + \sqrt{2}B_{21}W + \sqrt{2}B_{23}W + \sqrt{2}B_{32}W - 3\sqrt{2}E_{10}W + 3\sqrt{2}E_{30}W - 2\sqrt{2}h_1W + 2\sqrt{2}h_3W \\ & \quad + 2i\epsilon E_{13} - 2i\epsilon E_{22} + 2i\epsilon E_{31} - 12i\epsilon h_0 + 2ikB_{11} - 2ikB_{33} + 6ikE_{20} + 4ikh_2 = 0; \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3W - \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - ikf_0 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 - E_{20} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_1W + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_3W + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 + \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 - ikc_2 + B_{11} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_1W + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3W + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 + i\epsilon c_2 + E_{31} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1W + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}d_3W - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 - \frac{1}{3}ikd_2 - i\epsilon c_2 - E_{13} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_1W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}d_3W - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon f_0 + i\epsilon f_2 + \frac{2}{3}ikd_2 + E_{22} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}c_1W + \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_3W - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_2 - \frac{1}{3}ikf_2 + ikc_2 + B_{33} = 0, \\ & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1W + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3W - B_{22} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1W + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3W - B_{20} = 0; \end{aligned}$$

$$\underline{V_2, S_2, P_2}, \quad \sqrt{2}c_2W - \sqrt{2}f_1W - \frac{3}{2}\sqrt{2}hW + 2ikc_3 + 2i\epsilon d_1 = 6h_1;$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sqrt{2}B_{11}W - \sqrt{2}B_{22}W + \sqrt{2}B_{31}W - 2\sqrt{2}h_2W - 2i\epsilon E_{12} - 2i\epsilon E_{21} + 2ikB_{32} + 4ikh_1 = 0, \\
 & -\sqrt{2}B_{20}W - \sqrt{2}E_{11}W + \sqrt{2}E_{31}W - 2\sqrt{2}h_0W + 2ikB_{30} + 2ikE_{21} - 2i\epsilon E_{10} - 4i\epsilon h_1 = 0; \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2W - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0W - \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + E_{10} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_1W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2W + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2W + \frac{2}{3}ikc_3 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 + B_{32} = 0, \\
 & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2W + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_1W + \frac{1}{3}ikc_3 + \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_1 - B_{21} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2W - i\epsilon c_3 - E_{12} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2W + ikd_1 + B_{30} = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_3 + ikd_1 + E_{21} = 0;
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\underline{V_3, S_3, P_3}, \quad -\sqrt{2}c_2W + \sqrt{2}f_3W + 2ikc_1 + 2i\epsilon d_3 = 6h_3,$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sqrt{2}B_{13}W - \sqrt{2}B_{22}W + \sqrt{2}B_{33}W + 2\sqrt{2}h_2W - 2i\epsilon E_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{32} - 2ikB_{12} + 4ikh_3 = 0, \\
 & -\sqrt{2}B_{20}W - \sqrt{2}E_{13}W + \sqrt{2}E_{33}W + 2\sqrt{2}h_0W - 2ikB_{10} + 2ikE_{23} - 2i\epsilon E_{30} - 4i\epsilon h_3 = 0; \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3W + \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_0W - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 + \frac{2}{3}i\epsilon d_3 + E_{30} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}c_2W - \frac{1}{3\sqrt{2}}f_3W - \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}f_2W + \frac{2}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 - B_{12} = 0, \\
 & \frac{2}{3}\sqrt{2}c_2W + \frac{1}{3}\sqrt{2}f_3W - \frac{1}{3}ikc_1 - \frac{1}{3}i\epsilon d_3 - B_{23} = 0, \\
 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2W - ikd_3 + B_{10} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_2W + i\epsilon c_1 + E_{32} = 0, \quad i\epsilon c_1 + ikd_3 + E_{23} = 0;
 \end{aligned}$$

V_4, S_4, P_4

$$B_{21}W + 2h_1W - \sqrt{2}ikB_{31} + \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{11} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_1W - i\epsilon f_1 - E_{11} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_3W + ikf_1 + B_{31} = 0;$$

V_5, S_5, P_5

$$-B_{23}W + 2h_3W - \sqrt{2}ikB_{13} - \sqrt{2}i\epsilon E_{33} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}d_3W + i\epsilon f_3 + E_{33} = 0, \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}c_1W - ikf_3 + B_{13} = 0.$$

Eliminating the variables referring to the tensors of the first and third ranks

$$\begin{aligned}
 & h_0, h_2, \quad h_1 = 0, \quad h_3 = 0; \quad E_{20}, B_{11}, E_{31}, E_{13}, E_{22}, B_{33}, B_{22}, B_{20}; \\
 & E_{10}, B_{32}, B_{21}, E_{12}, B_{30}, E_{21}; \quad E_{30}, B_{12}, B_{23}, B_{10}, E_{32}, E_{23}; \quad E_{11}, B_{31}; \quad E_{33}, B_{13},
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.7}$$

we should get 13 equations for 11 variables $f_1, f_2, f_3, c_1, c_2, c_3, d_1, d_2, d_3, f_0$. After performing the needed calculations we derive a homogeneous system of 13 equations, its rank is equal to 5. Further we obtain the linear nonhomogeneous system of 5 equations for 5 functions (with non-vanishing

determinant). Its solution has the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \begin{vmatrix} h \\ f_2 \\ c_2 \\ d_1 \\ d_3 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \end{vmatrix} f_1 + \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \end{vmatrix} f_3 + \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}} \\ \frac{\sqrt{2k}}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \end{vmatrix} c_1 \\
 & + \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}} \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \end{vmatrix} c_3 + \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{k} \\ \frac{k\epsilon}{k^2-\epsilon^2} \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \end{vmatrix} d_2 + \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2} \\ \frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \end{vmatrix} f_0. \tag{2.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

This formula describes 6 independent solutions. Let us choose them as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Psi = & \begin{vmatrix} h \\ f_1 \\ f_2 \\ f_3 \\ c_1 \\ c_2 \\ c_3 \\ d_1 \\ d_2 \\ d_3 \\ f_0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}} \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \\
 \Psi_4 = & \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 1 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_5 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{k} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k\epsilon}{k^2-\epsilon^2} \\ 0 \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 1 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_6 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}} \\ 1 \end{vmatrix}. \tag{2.9}
 \end{aligned}$$

Taking in mind the structure of the basic tensor

$$H_2 = \{f_1\varphi_4, f_2\varphi_1, f_3\varphi_5, c_1\varphi_3, c_2\varphi_1, c_3\varphi_2, d_1\varphi_2, d_2\varphi_1, d_3\varphi_3, f_0\varphi_1\} \tag{2.10}$$

these 6 solutions can be presented as follows:

$$h(r) = 0, \quad \Psi_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \varphi_4(r) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}}\varphi_2(r) \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}}\varphi_3(r) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \varphi_5(r) \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}}\varphi_2(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2\epsilon}}\varphi_3(r) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ \varphi_3(r) \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}\varphi_2(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}\varphi_3(r) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\Psi_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_1(r) \\ \varphi_2(r) \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}\varphi_2(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}\varphi_3(r) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{k}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k\epsilon}{k^2-\epsilon^2}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_2(r) \\ \varphi_1(r) \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_3(r) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Psi_6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2}\varphi_1(r) \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_2(r) \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}\varphi_3(r) \\ \varphi_1(r) \end{pmatrix}.$$

The functions φ_i may be presented in Bessel form

$$\varphi_1 = L_1 J_{|m|}, \quad \varphi_2 = L_2 J_{|m-1|}, \quad \varphi_3 = L_3 J_{|m+1|}, \quad \varphi_4 = L_4 J_{|m-2|}, \quad \varphi_5 = L_5 J_{|m+2|}. \quad (2.11)$$

Differential constraints in the variable $z = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} r$ read

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)\varphi_2 &= i\varphi_1, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)\varphi_1 &= i\varphi_2; \\ \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)\varphi_3 &= i\varphi_1, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)\varphi_1 &= i\varphi_3; \\ \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-2}{z}\right)\varphi_4 &= i\varphi_2, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m-1}{z}\right)\varphi_2 &= i\varphi_4; \\ \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+2}{z}\right)\varphi_5 &= i\varphi_3, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m+1}{z}\right)\varphi_3 &= i\varphi_5. \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Taking in mind the formulas

$$\varphi_1 = L_1 J_{|m|}, \quad \varphi_2 = L_2 J_{|m-1|}, \quad \varphi_3 = L_3 J_{|m+1|}, \quad \varphi_4 = L_4 J_{|m-2|}, \quad \varphi_5 = L_5 J_{|m+2|}. \quad (2.13)$$

we rewrite the above constraints in the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_2J_{|m-1|} = iL_1J_{|m|}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)L_1J_{|m|} = iL_2J_{|m-1|}; \\
 & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3J_{|m+1|} = iL_1J_{|m|}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)L_1J_{|m|} = iL_3J_{|m+1|}; \\
 & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-2}{z}\right)L_4J_{|m-2|} = iL_2J_{|m-1|}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_2J_{|m-1|} = iL_4J_{|m-2|}; \\
 & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+2}{z}\right)L_5J_{|m+2|} = iL_3J_{|m+1|}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3J_{|m+1|} = iL_5J_{|m+2|}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.14}$$

To avoid the presence of the modulus in the formulas, we split them in two groups

$$\begin{aligned}
 I & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_2J_{m-1} = iL_1J_m, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)L_1J_m = iL_2J_{m-1}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3J_{m+1} = iL_1J_m, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)L_1J_m = iL_3J_{m+1}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-2}{z}\right)L_4J_{m-2} = iL_2J_{m-1}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_2J_{m-1} = iL_4J_{m-2}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+2}{z}\right)L_5J_{m+2} = iL_3J_{m+1}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3J_{m+1} = iL_5J_{m+2};
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 II & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{-(m-1)}{z}\right)L'_2J_{-(m-1)} = iL'_1J_{-m}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{-m}{z}\right)L'_1J_{-m} = iL'_2J_{-(m-1)}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{-(m+1)}{z}\right)L'_3J_{-(m+1)} = iL'_1J_{-m}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{-m}{z}\right)L'_1J_{-m} = iL'_3J_{-(m+1)}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{-(m-2)}{z}\right)L'_4J_{-(m-2)} = iL'_2J_{-(m-1)}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{-(m-1)}{z}\right)L'_2J_{-(m-1)} = iL'_4J_{-(m-2)}; \\
 & \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{-(m+2)}{z}\right)L'_5J_{-(m+2)} = iL'_3J_{-(m+1)}, & \left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{-(m+1)}{z}\right)L'_3J_{-(m+1)} = iL'_5J_{-(m+2)}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

Applying the known properties of the Bessel functions

$$\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{p}{z}\right)J_p = J_{p-1}, \quad \left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{p}{z}\right)J_p = -J_{p+1}; \tag{2.17}$$

we derive algebraic relations between coefficients

$$I \quad L_2 = -iL_1, \quad L_3 = iL_1, \quad L_4 = -L_1, \quad L_5 = -L_1, \tag{2.18}$$

$$II \quad L'_2 = iL'_1, \quad L'_3 = -iL'_1, \quad L'_4 = -L'_1, \quad L'_5 = -L'_1. \tag{2.19}$$

Therefore, five basic functions are determined by the following relations

$$\begin{aligned}
 I & \quad \varphi_1 = L_1J_m, \varphi_2 = -iL_1J_{m-1}, \varphi_3 = iL_1J_{m+1}, \varphi_4 = -L_1J_{m-2}, \varphi_5 = -L_1J_{m+2}; \\
 II & \quad \varphi_1 = L'_1J_{-m}, \varphi_2 = iL'_1J_{-(m-1)}, \varphi_3 = -iL'_1J_{-(m+1)}, \varphi_4 = -L'_1J_{-(m-2)}, \varphi_5 = -L'_1J_{-(m+2)}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Let us turn back to six independent solutions, they may be presented in Bessel form (let $L_1 = 1$

and $L'_1 = 1$):

$$I, \quad h(r) = 0, \quad \Psi_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ -J_{m-2} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}J_m \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{m-1} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{m+1} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -J_{m+2} \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}J_m \\ 0 \\ +\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{m-1} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{m+1} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2}k}J_m \\ 0 \\ \frac{iJ_{m+1}}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}J_m \\ 0 \\ +\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{m-1} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{m+1} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

$$I, \quad \Psi_4 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2}k}J_m \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}J_m \\ -iJ_{m-1} \\ +\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{m-1} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{m+1} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_5 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{k}J_m \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k\epsilon}{k^2-\epsilon^2}J_m \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}iJ_{m-1} \\ J_m \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}iJ_{m+1} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_6 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2}J_m \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}iJ_{m-1} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}iJ_{m+1} \\ J_m \end{vmatrix}. \quad (2.20)$$

$$II, \quad h(r) = 0, \quad \Psi_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ -J_{-(m-2)} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -J_{-(m+2)} \\ 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ 0 \\ +\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{2\sqrt{2}\epsilon}iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_3 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2}k}J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{iJ_{-(m+1)}}{\sqrt{2\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}}J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ 0 \\ +\frac{k}{2\epsilon}iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix},$$

$$II, \quad \Psi_4 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}}{\sqrt{2k}} J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} J_{-m} \\ iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ -\frac{k}{2\epsilon} iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ 0 \\ +\frac{k}{2\epsilon} iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_5 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -\frac{\epsilon}{k} J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{k\epsilon}{k^2-\epsilon^2} J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ J_{-m} \\ +\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Psi_6 = \begin{vmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2} J_{-m} \\ 0 \\ \frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} iJ_{-(m-1)} \\ 0 \\ +\frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} iJ_{-(m+1)} \\ J_{-m} \end{vmatrix}. \quad (2.21)$$

3. Gauge solutions for massless spin 2 field

Below we will take into account the structure of 6 independent solutions (2.20) and (2.21).

As known, for massless spin 2 field there exist gauge solutions, which are defined through an arbitrary vector $L_c^C(x)$, $c = 0, 1, 2, 3$; the symbol $C = (\text{Cart})$ designates Cartesian basis. In this way, the gauge scalar field $\bar{h}(x)$ is given by the formula (the bar symbol refers to gauge solutions)

$$\bar{h}(x) = \bar{\Phi} = \partial_t L_0^C - (\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}) L_1^C - \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C - \partial_z L_3^C; \quad (3.1)$$

in turn, 10 components of the gauge symmetric tensor are given by the formula

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{f}_1 &= \bar{\Phi}_{11} = 2\partial_r L_1^C + \frac{1}{2}[\partial_t L_0^C - (\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}) L_1^C - \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C - \partial_z L_3^C], \\ \bar{f}_2 &= \bar{\Phi}_{22} = \frac{2}{r} L_1^C + \frac{2}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C + \frac{1}{2}[\partial_t L_0^C - (\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}) L_1^C - \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C - \partial_z L_3^C], \\ \bar{f}_3 &= \bar{\Phi}_{33} = 2\partial_z L_3^C + \frac{1}{2}[\partial_t L_0^C - (\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}) L_1^C - \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C - \partial_z L_3^C], \\ \bar{c}_1 &= \bar{\Phi}_{23} = \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_3^C + \partial_z L_2^C, \quad \bar{c}_2 = \bar{\Phi}_{31} = \partial_z L_1^C + \partial_r L_3^C, \quad \bar{c}_3 = \bar{\Phi}_{12} = -\frac{1}{r} L_2^C + \partial_r L_2^C + \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_1^C, \\ \bar{d}_1 &= \bar{\Phi}_{01} = \partial_t L_1^C + \partial_r L_0^C, \quad \bar{d}_2 = \bar{\Phi}_{02} = \partial_t L_2^C + \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_0^C, \quad \bar{d}_3 = \bar{\Phi}_{03} = \partial_t L_3^C + \partial_z L_0^C; \\ \bar{f}_0 &= \bar{\Phi}_{00} = 2\partial_t L_0^C - \frac{1}{2}[\partial_t L_0^C - (\partial_r + \frac{1}{r}) L_1^C - \frac{1}{r} \partial_\phi L_2^C - \partial_z L_3^C], \end{aligned}$$

these relations refer to Cartesian basis. Taking into account expressions for the gauge vector $L_c^C(x)$

$$L^C(t, r, \varphi, z) = e^{-ict} e^{im\varphi} e^{ikz} \begin{vmatrix} L_0^C \\ L_1^C \\ L_2^C \\ L_3^C \end{vmatrix} = e^{-ict} e^{im\varphi} e^{ikz} \begin{vmatrix} L_0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 - L_1) \\ \frac{-i}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1) \\ L_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

(the quantities without the symbol C refer to cyclic basis), the previous formulas transform to the

following form (the total multiplier $e^{-i\epsilon t} e^{im\phi} e^{ikz}$ is omitted):

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{h}(r) &= -i\epsilon L_0^C - \left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)L_1^C - \frac{im}{r}L_2^C - ikL_3^C; \\ \bar{f}_1(r) &= 2\frac{d}{dr}L_1^C - \frac{1}{2}i\epsilon L_0^C - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)L_1^C - \frac{im}{2r}L_2^C - \frac{1}{2}ikL_3^C, \\ \bar{f}_2(r) &= \frac{2}{r}L_1^C + \frac{2im}{r}L_2^C - \frac{1}{2}i\epsilon L_0^C - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)L_1^C - \frac{im}{2r}L_2^C - \frac{1}{2}ikL_3^C, \\ \bar{f}_3(r) &= 2ikL_3^C - \frac{1}{2}i\epsilon L_0^C - \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)L_1^C - \frac{im}{2r}L_2^C - \frac{1}{2}ikL_3^C; \\ \bar{c}_1(r) &= \frac{im}{r}L_3^C + ikL_2^C, \quad \bar{c}_2(r) = ikL_1^C + \frac{d}{dr}L_3^C, \quad \bar{c}_3(r) = -\frac{1}{r}L_2^C + \frac{d}{dr}L_2^C + \frac{im}{r}L_1^C; \\ \bar{d}_1(r) &= -i\epsilon L_1^C + \frac{d}{dr}L_0^C, \quad \bar{d}_2(r) = -i\epsilon L_2^C + \frac{im}{r}L_0^C, \quad \bar{d}_3(r) = -i\epsilon L_3^C + ikL_0^C; \\ \bar{f}_0(r) &= -2i\epsilon L_0^C + \frac{1}{2}i\epsilon L_0^C + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)L_1^C + \frac{im}{2r}L_2^C + \frac{1}{2}ikL_3^C. \end{aligned}$$

The right sides of this relations should be transformed to cyclic basis, this results in

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{h}(r) &= -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) - \frac{m}{r\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1) - i\epsilon L_0 - ikL_2; \\ \bar{f}_1(r) &= +\sqrt{2}\frac{d}{dr}(L_3 - L_1) - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) - \frac{m}{2\sqrt{2}r}(L_3 + L_1) - \frac{i\epsilon}{2}L_0 - \frac{ik}{2}L_2, \\ \bar{f}_2(r) &= -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{r}(L_3 - L_1) + \frac{\sqrt{2}m}{r}(L_3 + L_1) - \frac{m}{2\sqrt{2}r}(L_3 + L_1) - \frac{i\epsilon}{2}L_0 - \frac{ik}{2}L_2, \\ \bar{f}_3(r) &= -\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) - \frac{m}{2\sqrt{2}r}(L_3 + L_1) + 2ikL_2 - \frac{i\epsilon}{2}L_0 - \frac{ik}{2}L_2; \\ \bar{c}_1(r) &= \frac{im}{r}L_2 + \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1), \quad \bar{c}_2(r) = \frac{d}{dr}L_2 + \frac{ik}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 - L_1), \\ \bar{c}_3(r) &= -\frac{i}{\sqrt{2}}\frac{d}{dr}(L_3 + L_1) + \frac{i}{r\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1) + \frac{im}{r\sqrt{2}}(L_3 - L_1); \\ \bar{d}_1(r) &= +\frac{d}{dr}L_0 - \frac{i\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 - L_1), \quad \bar{d}_2(r) = +\frac{im}{r}L_0 - \frac{\epsilon}{\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1), \quad \bar{d}_3(r) = -i\epsilon L_2 + ikL_0; \\ \bar{f}_0(r) &= +\frac{1}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) + \frac{m}{2\sqrt{2}r}(L_3 + L_1) - 2i\epsilon L_0 + \frac{i\epsilon}{2}L_0 + \frac{ik}{2}L_2. \end{aligned}$$

Recall that the quantities in the left sides refer to Cartesian basis. For symmetric tensor, transition to cyclic basis is performed by means of the known linear transformation with the following matrix

$$\bar{H}_2^{cycl} = C_2 \bar{H}_2^{Cart} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & -2i & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & 2 & \cdot \\ 1 & -1 & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & 2i & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & i\sqrt{2} & \sqrt{2} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ -1 & -1 & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & i\sqrt{2} & -\sqrt{2} & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & -\sqrt{2} & i\sqrt{2} & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & 2 & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \sqrt{2} & i\sqrt{2} & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & 2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{f}_1 \\ \bar{f}_2 \\ \bar{f}_3 \\ \bar{c}_1 \\ \bar{c}_2 \\ \bar{c}_3 \\ \bar{d}_1 \\ \bar{d}_2 \\ \bar{d}_3 \\ \bar{f}_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

where, for brevity, we denote vanishing elements by dots. After calculation we obtain expressions for 10 components of the symmetric tensor in cyclic basis

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{f}_1 &= -\sqrt{2}a_{m-1}L_1, & \bar{f}_3 &= \sqrt{2}b_{m+1}L_3, \\
 \bar{f}_2 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}b_{m-1}L_1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}a_{m+1}L_3 - \frac{1}{2}i(\epsilon L_0 - 3kL_2), \\
 \bar{c}_1 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}b_mL_2 + ikL_3, & \bar{c}_3 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}a_mL_2 + ikL_1, \\
 \bar{c}_2 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}b_{m-1}L_1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}a_{m+1}L_3 + \frac{1}{2}i(\epsilon L_0 + kL_2), \\
 \bar{d}_1 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}a_mL_0 - i\epsilon L_1, & \bar{d}_2 &= i(kL_0 - \epsilon L_2), & \bar{d}_3 &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}b_mL_0 - i\epsilon L_3, \\
 \bar{f}_0 &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}b_{m-1}L_1 + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}a_{m+1}L_3 - \frac{1}{2}i(3\epsilon L_0 - kL_2).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

In [30], for massless spin 1 field four independent solutions in cylindric coordinates were found. First consider three of them (they refer to cyclic basis):

$$\begin{aligned}
 1, & \quad \Phi_0 = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad \underline{\Phi_1 = 1}, \quad \Phi_2 = 0, \quad \Phi_3 = 0; \\
 2, & \quad \Phi_0 = -\frac{k}{\epsilon}, \quad \Phi_1 = 0, \quad \underline{\Phi_2 = 1}, \quad \Phi_3 = 0; \\
 3, & \quad \Phi_0 = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad \Phi_1 = 0, \quad \Phi_2 = 0, \quad \underline{\Phi_3 = 1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.4}$$

We can write down explicit expressions for three gauge vectors $L_c^{(1,2,3)}$ in terms of Bessel functions? spitting them in two groups , *I* and *II* (recall that $z = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} r$; let $\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} = \lambda$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1^{(1)}(z) &= -i J_{m-1}(z), L_2^{(1)}(z) = 0, L_3^{(1)}(z) = 0, L_0^{(1)}(z) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_m(z); \\
 I, & \quad L_1^{(2)}(z) = 0, L_2^{(2)}(z) = J_m(z), L_3^{(2)}(z) = 0, L_0^{(2)}(z) = -\frac{k}{\epsilon} J_m(z); \\
 L_1^{(3)}(z) &= 0, L_2^{(3)}(z) = 0, L_3^{(3)}(z) = +i J_{m+1}(z), L_0^{(3)}(z) = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_m(z);
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1^{(1)}(z) &= +i J_{-m+1}(z), L_2^{(1)}(z) = 0, L_3^{(1)}(z) = 0, L_0^{(1)}(z) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_{-m}(z); \\
 II, & \quad L_1^{(2)}(z) = 0, L_2^{(2)}(z) = J_{-m}(z), L_3^{(2)}(z) = 0, L_0^{(2)}(z) = -\frac{k}{\epsilon} J_{-m}(z); \\
 L_1^{(3)}(z) &= 0, L_2^{(3)}(z) = 0, L_3^{(3)}(z) = -i J_{-m-1}(z), L_0^{(3)}(z) = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_{-m}(z).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

In the above expressions for 10 components of gauge tensor (3.3) we should change the variable $r \Rightarrow z$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{f}_1(z) &= -\sqrt{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_1(z), & \bar{f}_3(z) &= \sqrt{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3(z), \\
 \bar{f}_2(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_1(z) - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3(z) - \frac{1}{2}i(\epsilon L_0(z) - 3kL_2(z)), \\
 \bar{c}_1(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)L_2(z) + ikL_3(z), & \bar{c}_3(z) &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)L_2(z) + ikL_1(z), \\
 \bar{c}_2(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_1(z) - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3(z) + \frac{1}{2}i(\epsilon L_0 + kL_2(z)), \\
 \bar{d}_1(z) &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)L_0(z) - i\epsilon L_1(z), & \bar{d}_3(z) &= \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)L_0(z) - i\epsilon L_3(z), \\
 & & \bar{d}_2(z) &= i(kL_0(z) - \epsilon L_2(z)), \\
 \bar{f}_0(z) &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)L_1(z) + \frac{\sqrt{2}}{4}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m+1}{z}\right)L_3(z) - \frac{1}{2}i(3\epsilon L_0(z) - kL_2(z)).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

Let us substitute in these formulas expressions for vectors $L_c^{(1)}, L_c^{(2)}, L_c^{(3)}$. In this way, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, L_c^{(1)} \\
 \bar{f}_1 &= i\sqrt{2}\lambda\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m-1}{z}\right)J_{m-1}, & \bar{f}_2 &= -\frac{i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)J_{m-1} - \frac{i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}J_m, & \bar{f}_3 &= 0, \\
 \bar{c}_1 &= 0, & \bar{c}_2 &= -\frac{i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)J_{m-1} + \frac{i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}J_m, & \bar{c}_3 &= kJ_{m-1}, \\
 \bar{d}_1 &= -\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{m}{z}\right)J_m - \epsilon J_{m-1}, & \bar{d}_2 &= ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_m, & \bar{d}_3 &= \frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m}{z}\right)J_m, \\
 \bar{f}_0 &= \frac{i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dz} - \frac{m-1}{z}\right)J_{m-1} - \frac{3i\lambda}{2\sqrt{2}}J_m;
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

whence allowing the properties of Bessel functions we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, L_c^{(1)} \\
 \bar{f}_1 &= i\sqrt{2}\lambda J_{m-2}, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = 0, \bar{c}_1 = 0, \bar{c}_2 = \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_m, \bar{c}_3 = kJ_{m-1}, \\
 \bar{d}_1 &= -\left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_m, \bar{d}_3 = -\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{m+1}, \bar{f}_0 = -i\sqrt{2}\lambda J_m.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

Similarly we consider two remaining cases

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, L_c^{(2)} \\
 \bar{f}_1 &= 0, \bar{f}_2 = 2ikJ_m, \bar{f}_3 = 0, \bar{c}_1 = -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = 0, \bar{c}_3 = -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_{m-1}, \\
 \bar{d}_1 &= \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}}J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = -i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right)J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}}J_{m+1}, \bar{f}_0 = 2ikJ_m.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, L_c^{(3)} \\
 \bar{f}_1 &= 0, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = -\sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{m+2}, \bar{c}_1 = -kJ_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}i\lambda J_m, \bar{c}_3 = 0, \\
 \bar{d}_1 &= \frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = -ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{m+1}, \bar{f}_0 = \sqrt{2}i\lambda J_m.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.11}$$

For the variant *II* we obtain similar results:

$$\begin{aligned}
 II, L_c^{(1)}, \quad & \bar{f}_1 = \sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{-m+2}, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = 0, \bar{c}_1 = 0, \bar{c}_2 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}i\lambda J_{-m}, \bar{c}_3 = -kJ_{-m+1}, \\
 & \bar{d}_1 = \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{-m+1}, \bar{d}_2 = \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_{-m}, \bar{d}_3 = \frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{-m-1}, \bar{f}_0 = -\sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{-m}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 II, L_c^{(2)}, \quad & \bar{f}_1 = 0, \bar{f}_2 = 2ikJ_{-m}, \bar{f}_3 = 0, \bar{c}_1 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda J_{-m-1}, \bar{c}_2 = 0, \bar{c}_3 = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda J_{-m+1}, \\
 & \bar{d}_1 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda \frac{k}{\epsilon}J_{-m+1}, \bar{d}_2 = -i\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{-m}, \bar{d}_3 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda \frac{k}{\epsilon}J_{-m-1}, \bar{f}_0 = 2ikJ_{-m}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.13}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 II, L_c^{(3)}, \quad & \bar{f}_1 = 0, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = -\sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{-m-2}, \bar{c}_1 = kJ_{-m-1}, \bar{c}_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}i\lambda J_{-m}, \bar{c}_3 = 0, \\
 & \bar{d}_1 = -\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{-m+1}, \bar{d}_2 = -ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_{-m}, \bar{d}_3 = -\left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{-m-1}, \bar{f}_0 = \sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{-m}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.14}$$

There exists the fourth solution for spin 1 particle (of the gradient form), which also should be used when finding all gauge solutions for spin 2 particle. Let us designate it as $L_c^{(0)}$, it is defined by relations (the parameter L be fixed later)

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, \quad & \bar{L}_0^{(0)}(z) = -i\epsilon L J_m(z), \quad \bar{L}_2^{(0)}(z) = ikL J_m(z), \\
 \bar{L}_1^{(0)}(z) = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}}L J_{m-1}(z), \quad & \bar{L}_3^{(0)}(z) = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}}L J_{m+1}(z); \\
 II, \quad & \bar{L}_0^{(0)} = -i\epsilon L J_{-m}, \quad \bar{L}_2^{(0)} = ikL J_{-m}, \\
 \bar{L}_1^{(0)}(z) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}}L J_{-m+1}(z), \quad & \bar{L}_3^{(0)}(z) = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}}L J_{-m-1}(z).
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.15}$$

We substitute these expressions in the formula for components of the gauge tensor. This results in

$$\begin{aligned}
 I, L_c^{(0)}, \quad & \bar{f}_1 = \lambda^2 L J_{m-2}, \bar{f}_2 = -2k^2 L J_m, \bar{f}_3 = \lambda^2 L J_{m+2}, \\
 & \bar{c}_1 = -\sqrt{2}ik\lambda L J_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = \lambda^2 L J_m, \bar{c}_3 = -\sqrt{2}ik\lambda L J_{m-1}, \\
 & \bar{d}_1 = \sqrt{2}i\epsilon\lambda L J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = 2k\epsilon L J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \sqrt{2}i\epsilon\lambda L J_{m+1}, \bar{f}_0 = -2\epsilon^2 L J_m.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 II, L_c^{(0)}, \quad & \bar{f}_1 = \lambda^2 L J_{-m+2}, \bar{f}_2 = -2k^2 L J_{-m}, \bar{f}_3 = \lambda^2 L J_{-m-2}, \\
 & \bar{c}_1 = \sqrt{2}ik\lambda L J_{-m-1}, \bar{c}_2 = \lambda^2 L J_{-m}, \bar{c}_3 = \sqrt{2}ik\lambda L J_{-m+1}, \\
 & \bar{d}_1 = -\sqrt{2}i\epsilon\lambda L J_{-m+1}, \bar{d}_2 = 2k\epsilon L J_{-m}, \bar{d}_3 = -\sqrt{2}i\epsilon\lambda L J_{-m-1}, \bar{f}_0 = -2\epsilon^2 L J_{-m}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.17}$$

In order to have the same dimension for all four solutions we set $L = 1/\lambda$.

4. Verifying the gauge solutions

Let us write down all 6 solutions for massless spin 2 particle (further we follow only the case *I*). With 4 vectors, $L_c^{(1)}, L_c^{(2)}, L_c^{(3)}, L_c^{(0)}$ we may associate corresponding 10-dimensional columns Q, R, S, T

with the structure $\{f_i, c_i, d_i, f_0\}$:

$$L_c^{(1)} \implies Q, \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{f}_1 &= i\sqrt{2}\lambda J_{m-2}, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = 0, & \bar{c}_1 &= 0, \bar{c}_2 = \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_m, \bar{c}_3 = kJ_{m-1}, \\ \bar{d}_1 &= -\left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_m, \bar{d}_3 = -\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{m+1}, & \bar{f}_0 &= -i\sqrt{2}\lambda J_m; \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

$$L_c^{(2)} \implies R, \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{f}_1 &= 0, \bar{f}_2 = 2ikJ_m, \bar{f}_3 = 0, & \bar{c}_1 &= -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = 0, \bar{c}_3 = -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}J_{m-1}, \\ \bar{d}_1 &= \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}}J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = -i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right)J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}}J_{m+1}, & \bar{f}_0 &= 2ikJ_m; \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

$$L_c^{(3)} \implies S, \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{f}_1 &= 0, \bar{f}_2 = 0, \bar{f}_3 = -\sqrt{2}i\lambda J_{m+2}, & \bar{c}_1 &= -kJ_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}i\lambda J_m, \bar{c}_3 = 0, \\ \bar{d}_1 &= \frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon}J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = -ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right)J_{m+1}, & \bar{f}_0 &= \sqrt{2}i\lambda J_m. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3)$$

$$L_c^{(0)} \implies T, \quad \begin{aligned} \bar{f}_1 &= \lambda J_{m-2}, \bar{f}_2 = -2\frac{k^2}{\lambda}J_m, \bar{f}_3 = \lambda J_{m+2}, \\ \bar{c}_1 &= -\sqrt{2}ikJ_{m+1}, \bar{c}_2 = \lambda J_m, \bar{c}_3 = -\sqrt{2}ikJ_{m-1}, \\ \bar{d}_1 &= \sqrt{2}i\epsilon J_{m-1}, \bar{d}_2 = 2\frac{\epsilon k}{\lambda}J_m, \bar{d}_3 = \sqrt{2}i\epsilon J_{m+1}, \bar{f}_0 = -\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}J_m. \end{aligned} \quad (4.4)$$

These columns Q, R, S, T should be decomposed in linear combinations of the solutions $\Psi_i, i = 1, \dots, 6$:

$$\begin{aligned} Q &= q_1\Psi_1 + q_2\Psi_2 + q_3\Psi_3 + q_4\Psi_4 + q_5\Psi_5 + q_6\Psi_6, \\ R &= r_1\Psi_1 + r_2\Psi_2 + r_3\Psi_3 + r_4\Psi_4 + r_5\Psi_5 + r_6\Psi_6, \\ S &= s_1\Psi_1 + s_2\Psi_2 + s_3\Psi_3 + s_4\Psi_4 + s_5\Psi_5 + s_6\Psi_6, \\ T &= t_1\Psi_1 + t_2\Psi_2 + t_3\Psi_3 + t_4\Psi_4 + t_5\Psi_5 + t_6\Psi_6; \end{aligned} \quad (4.5)$$

whence we derive 4 algebraic systems. The first system has the form

$$Q, \quad \begin{aligned} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda &= q_1, & 0 &= \sqrt{2}(q_4 - q_3)\lambda - 2q_5\epsilon, & 0 &= -q_2, & 0 &= iq_3, \\ \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} &= q_1\lambda^2 + q_2\lambda^2 + \sqrt{2}q_3k\lambda - \sqrt{2}q_4k\lambda - 2q_5k\epsilon - 2q_6\epsilon^2, \\ k &= -iq_4, & -\left(\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} + \epsilon\right) &= -i\frac{\sqrt{2}(q_1 - q_2)\lambda^2 - 2(q_3 + q_4)k\lambda + 2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(q_5k + q_6\epsilon)}{4\lambda\epsilon}, \\ ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} &= q_5, & -\frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon} &= i\frac{\sqrt{2}(q_1 - q_2)\lambda^2 - 2(q_3 + q_4)k\lambda - 2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(q_5k + q_6\epsilon)}{4\lambda\epsilon}, & -i\sqrt{2}\lambda &= q_6. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

Its solution reads (these expressions follow from simple equations, more complex equations turn out to become identities)

$$Q, \quad q_1 = -i\sqrt{2}\lambda, \quad q_2 = 0, \quad q_3 = 0, \quad q_4 = ik, \quad q_5 = ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad q_6 = -i\sqrt{2}\lambda. \quad (4.7)$$

The second system reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 R, \quad & 0 = -r_1, \quad 2ik = \frac{\sqrt{2}(r_4-r_3)\lambda-2r_5\epsilon}{2k}, \quad 0 = -r_2, \quad -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} = ir_3, \\
 & 0 = r_1\lambda^2 + r_2\lambda^2 + \sqrt{2}r_3k\lambda - \sqrt{2}r_4k\lambda - 2r_5k\epsilon - 2r_6\epsilon^2, \quad -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} = -ir_4, \\
 & \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}} = -i\frac{\sqrt{2}(r_1-r_2)\lambda^2-2(r_3+r_4)k\lambda+2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(r_5k+r_6\epsilon)}{4\lambda\epsilon}, \quad -i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right) = r_5, \\
 & \frac{k\lambda}{\epsilon\sqrt{2}} = i\frac{\sqrt{2}(r_1-r_2)\lambda^2-2(r_3+r_4)k\lambda-2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(r_5k+r_6\epsilon)}{4\lambda\epsilon}, \quad 2ik = r_6;
 \end{aligned}$$

its solution has the form

$$R, \quad r_1 = 0, \quad r_2 = 0, \quad r_3 = i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad r_4 = -i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad r_5 = -i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right), \quad r_6 = 2ik. \quad (4.8)$$

The third system reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 S, \quad & 0 = -s_1J_{m-2}, \quad 0 = \frac{\sqrt{2}(s_4-s_3)\lambda-2s_5\epsilon}{2k}J_m, \quad -i\sqrt{2}\lambda J_{m+2} = -s_2J_{m+2}, \quad -kJ_{m+1} = is_3J_{m+1}, \\
 & \frac{1}{2}(-\sqrt{2})i\lambda J_m = \frac{s_1\lambda^2+s_2\lambda^2+\sqrt{2}s_3k\lambda-\sqrt{2}s_4k\lambda-2s_5k\epsilon-2s_6\epsilon^2}{2\lambda^2}J_m, \quad 0 = -is_4J_{m-1}, \\
 & \frac{\lambda^2J_{m-1}}{2\epsilon} = -i\frac{\sqrt{2}(s_1-s_2)\lambda^2-2(s_3+s_4)k\lambda+2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(s_5k+s_6\epsilon)}{4\lambda\epsilon}J_{m-1}, \quad -\frac{ik\lambda J_m}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} = s_5J_m, \\
 & \epsilon\left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2}{2\epsilon^2}\right)J_{m+1} = i\frac{(\sqrt{2}(s_1-s_2)\lambda^2-2(s_3+s_4)k\lambda-2\sqrt{2}\epsilon(s_5k+s_6\epsilon))}{4\lambda\epsilon}J_{m+1}, \quad \sqrt{2}i\lambda J_m = s_6J_m;
 \end{aligned}$$

its solution reads

$$S, \quad s_1 = 0, \quad s_2 = i\sqrt{2}\lambda, \quad s_3 = -\frac{k}{i}, \quad s_4 = 0, \quad s_5 = -\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad s_6 = \sqrt{2}i\lambda. \quad (4.9)$$

The fourth system reads

$$\begin{aligned}
 T, \quad & t_1 = -\lambda, \quad \frac{\sqrt{2}(t_4-t_3)\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}-2t_5\epsilon}{2k} = -\frac{2k^2}{\lambda}, \quad t_2 = -\lambda, \quad t_3 = -\sqrt{2}k, \\
 & \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{(-\sqrt{2})kt_3\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+\sqrt{2}kt_4\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+2kt_5\epsilon+2t_6\epsilon^2}{k^2-\epsilon^2} + t_1 + t_2\right) = \lambda, \quad t_4 = \sqrt{2}k, \\
 & \frac{i(2kt_3\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+2kt_4\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+\sqrt{2}(t_2(\epsilon^2-k^2)+t_1(k-\epsilon)(k+\epsilon)-2\epsilon(kt_5+t_6\epsilon)))}{4\epsilon\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} = \sqrt{2}i\epsilon, \quad t_5 = \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}, \\
 & -\frac{i(2kt_3\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+2kt_4\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}+\sqrt{2}(t_2(\epsilon^2-k^2)+t_1(k-\epsilon)(k+\epsilon)+2\epsilon(kt_5+t_6\epsilon)))}{4\epsilon\sqrt{\epsilon^2-k^2}} = \sqrt{2}i\epsilon, \quad t_6 = -\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda};
 \end{aligned}$$

its solutions has the fom

$$T, \quad t_1 = -\lambda, \quad t_2 = -\lambda, \quad t_3 = -\sqrt{2}k, \quad t_4 = \sqrt{2}k, \quad t_5 = \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}, \quad t_6 = -\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}. \quad (4.10)$$

Let us write down all coefficients together

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q, \quad & q_1 = -i\sqrt{2}\lambda, \quad q_2 = 0, \quad q_3 = 0, \quad q_4 = ik, \quad q_5 = ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad q_6 = -i\sqrt{2}\lambda; \\
 R, \quad & r_1 = 0, \quad r_2 = 0, \quad r_3 = i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad r_4 = -i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad r_5 = -i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right), \quad r_6 = 2ik; \\
 S, \quad & s_1 = 0, \quad s_2 = i\sqrt{2}\lambda, \quad s_3 = -\frac{k}{i}, \quad s_4 = 0, \quad s_5 = -\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}, \quad s_6 = \sqrt{2}i\lambda; \\
 T, \quad & t_1 = -\lambda, \quad t_2 = -\lambda, \quad t_3 = -\sqrt{2}k, \quad t_4 = \sqrt{2}k, \quad t_5 = \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}, \quad t_6 = -\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}.
 \end{aligned} \quad (4.11)$$

so we have found 4 decompositions

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q &= -i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_1 + ik\Psi_4 + ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\Psi_5 - i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_6, \quad R = i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\Psi_3 - i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\Psi_4 - i\epsilon\left(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1\right)\Psi_5 + 2ik\Psi_6, \\
 S &= i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_2 - \frac{k}{i}\Psi_3 - \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\Psi_5 + \sqrt{2}i\lambda\Psi_6, \quad T = -\lambda\Psi_1 - \lambda\Psi_2 - \sqrt{2}k\Psi_3 + \sqrt{2}k\Psi_4 + \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}\Psi_5 - \frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}\Psi_6.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.12}$$

Because when finding 6 independent solutions in massless case it was shown that corresponding scalar function is equal to zero, $\bar{h}(r) = 0$, we have to calculate the component $\bar{h}(r)$ for each gauge vector $L_c^{(i)}$, $i = 1, 2, 3, 0$. First, we find the general expression for $\bar{h}(r)$:

$$\bar{h}(r) = -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dr} + \frac{1}{r}\right)(L_3 - L_1) - \frac{m}{r\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1) - i\epsilon L_0 - ikL_2; \tag{4.13}$$

in the variable $z = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} r$, $\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} = \lambda$ this equality reads

$$\bar{h}(z) = -\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\left(\frac{d}{dz} + \frac{1}{z}\right)(L_3 - L_1) - \lambda\frac{m}{z\sqrt{2}}(L_3 + L_1) - i\epsilon L_0 - ikL_2. \tag{4.14}$$

Taking in mind the equalities

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_1^{(1)} &= -i J_{m-1}, \quad L_2^{(1)} = 0, \quad L_3^{(1)} = 0, \quad L_0^{(1)} = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_m; \\
 L_1^{(2)} &= 0, \quad L_2^{(2)}(z) = J_m, \quad L_3^{(2)} = 0, \quad L_0^{(2)} = -\frac{k}{\epsilon} J_m; \\
 L_1^{(3)} &= 0, \quad L_2^{(3)} = 0, \quad L_3^{(3)} = +i J_{m+1}, \quad L_0^{(3)} = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} J_m; \\
 \bar{L}_0^{(0)} &= -i\epsilon L J_m, \quad \bar{L}_2^{(0)} = ikL J_m, \quad \bar{L}_1^{(0)} = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} L J_{m-1}, \quad \bar{L}_3^{(0)} = -\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} L J_{m+1},
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.15}$$

after performing needed calculations we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_c^{(1)}, \quad \bar{h}(z) &= i\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} J_m - i\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} J_m \equiv 0, \quad L_c^{(2)}, \quad \bar{h}(z) = ikJ_m - ikJ_m \equiv 0, \\
 L_c^{(3)}, \quad \bar{h}(z) &= -i\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} J_m + i\frac{\sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2}}{\sqrt{2}} J_m \equiv 0, \quad L_c^{(0)}, \bar{h}(z) = \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} J_m - \sqrt{\epsilon^2 - k^2} J_m \equiv 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.16}$$

We conclude that for all 4 cases the gauge component $\bar{h}(r)$ turns out to be vanishing.

The verifying of the gauge solutions of the type II gives the similar results (all details are omitted).

5. Eliminating the gauge degrees of freedom, variants I and II

As shown above, the four gauge solutions are decomposed on 6 independent solutions see (4.12). The six independent solutions Ψ_i can be considered as an orthogonal basis: $\Psi_i \cdot \Psi_j = \delta_{ij}$, $i, j \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$. Let us search two solutions, which are decomposed in combination of 6 vectors Ψ_i :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Phi^{(1)} &= \phi_1^{(1)}\Psi_1 + \phi_2^{(1)}\Psi_2 + \phi_3^{(1)}\Psi_3 + \phi_4^{(1)}\Psi_4 + \phi_5^{(1)}\Psi_5 + \phi_6^{(1)}\Psi_6, \\
 \Phi^{(2)} &= \phi_1^{(2)}\Psi_1 + \phi_2^{(2)}\Psi_2 + \phi_3^{(2)}\Psi_3 + \phi_4^{(2)}\Psi_4 + \phi_5^{(2)}\Psi_5 + \phi_6^{(2)}\Psi_6;
 \end{aligned} \tag{5.1}$$

besides these 2 solutions should be orthogonal to 4 gauge solutions

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi^{(1)} \cdot Q = 0, \quad \Phi^{(1)} \cdot R = 0, \quad \Phi^{(1)} \cdot S = 0, \quad \Phi^{(1)} \cdot T = 0; \\ \Phi^{(2)} \cdot Q = 0, \quad \Phi^{(2)} \cdot R = 0, \quad \Phi^{(2)} \cdot S = 0, \quad \Phi^{(2)} \cdot T = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{5.2}$$

It suffices to study only one equation (the index in brackets is omitted)

$$\Phi \cdot Q = 0, \quad \Phi \cdot R = 0, \quad \Phi \cdot S = 0, \quad \Phi \cdot T = 0. \tag{5.3}$$

In detailed form we get equations:

$$\begin{aligned} (\phi_1\Psi_1 + \phi_2\Psi_2 + \phi_3\Psi_3 + \phi_4\Psi_4 + \phi_5\Psi_5 + \phi_6\Psi_6)(-i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_1 + ik\Psi_4 + ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\Psi_5 - i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_6) = 0; \\ (\phi_1\Psi_1 + \phi_2\Psi_2 + \phi_3\Psi_3 + \phi_4\Psi_4 + \phi_5\Psi_5 + \phi_6\Psi_6)(i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\Psi_3 - i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\Psi_4 - i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1)\Psi_5 + 2ik\Psi_6) = 0; \\ (\phi_1\Psi_1 + \phi_2\Psi_2 + \phi_3\Psi_3 + \phi_4\Psi_4 + \phi_5\Psi_5 + \phi_6\Psi_6)(i\sqrt{2}\lambda\Psi_2 - \frac{k}{i}\Psi_3 - \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\Psi_5 + \sqrt{2}i\lambda\Psi_6) = 0; \\ (\phi_1\Psi_1 + \phi_2\Psi_2 + \phi_3\Psi_3 + \phi_4\Psi_4 + \phi_5\Psi_5 + \phi_6\Psi_6)(-\lambda\Psi_1 - \lambda\Psi_2 - \sqrt{2}k\Psi_3 + \sqrt{2}k\Psi_4 + \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}\Psi_5 - \frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}\Psi_6) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore from conditions (5.3) we derive algebraic system of 4 equations

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(-i\sqrt{2}\lambda) + \phi_4(ik) + \phi_5(ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}) + \phi_6(-i\sqrt{2}\lambda) = 0, \\ \phi_3(i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}) + \phi_4(-i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}) + \phi_5(-i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1)) + \phi_6^{(1)}(2ik) = 0, \\ \phi_2(i\sqrt{2}\lambda) + \phi_3(-\frac{k}{i}) + \phi_5(-\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}) + \phi_6(\sqrt{2}i\lambda) = 0, \\ \phi_1(-\lambda) + \phi_2(-\lambda) + \phi_3(-\sqrt{2}k) + \phi_4(\sqrt{2}k) + \phi_5(\frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda}) + \phi_6(-\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda}) = 0. \end{aligned} \tag{5.4}$$

This system may be presented in the matrix form $B_{4 \times 6}^{(1)}\Phi^{(1)} = 0$:

$$\begin{vmatrix} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda & . & . & ik & ik\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} & -i\sqrt{2}\lambda \\ . & . & i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} & -i\frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} & -i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1) & 2ik \\ . & i\sqrt{2}\lambda & -\frac{k}{i} & . & -\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} & \sqrt{2}i\lambda \\ -\lambda & -\lambda & -\sqrt{2}k & \sqrt{2}k & \frac{2k\epsilon}{\lambda} & -\frac{2\epsilon^2}{\lambda} \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \\ \phi_4 \\ \phi_5 \\ \phi_6 \end{vmatrix} = 0. \tag{5.5}$$

The rank of the matrix B equals 3. We readily verify that after eliminating the fourth row we obtain matrix with the same rank 3. Thus, we have an equivalent system

$$\begin{vmatrix} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & i\sqrt{2}\lambda & -\frac{k}{i} \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ \phi_3 \end{vmatrix} = -\phi_4 \begin{vmatrix} ik \\ -\frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} - \phi_5 \begin{vmatrix} \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} \\ -i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1) \\ -\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} \end{vmatrix} - \phi_6 \begin{vmatrix} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda \\ 2ik \\ \sqrt{2}i\lambda \end{vmatrix}. \tag{5.6}$$

Because all parameters $\phi_i, i = 1, \dots, 6$ are fixed up to an arbitrary total multiplier, we can set $\phi_3 = 1$. In this way, from (5.6) we derive the system

$$\begin{vmatrix} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & i\sqrt{2}\lambda & -\frac{k}{i} \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \\ 1 \end{vmatrix} = -\phi_4 \begin{vmatrix} ik \\ -\frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 \end{vmatrix} - \phi_5 \begin{vmatrix} \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} \\ -i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1) \\ -\frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon} \end{vmatrix} - \phi_6 \begin{vmatrix} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda \\ 2ik \\ \sqrt{2}i\lambda \end{vmatrix},$$

its solution is

$$\begin{aligned} -i\sqrt{2}\lambda\phi_1 &= -ik\phi_4 - \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\phi_5 + i\sqrt{2}\lambda\phi_6, \\ \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}} &= \frac{i\lambda}{\sqrt{2}}\phi_4 + i\epsilon(\frac{k^2}{\epsilon^2} + 1)\phi_5 - 2ik\phi_6, \quad i\sqrt{2}\lambda\phi_2 + ik = \frac{ik\lambda}{\sqrt{2}\epsilon}\phi_5 - i\sqrt{2}\lambda\phi_6. \end{aligned}$$

The second equation in (5.7) permits us to eliminate parameter ϕ_4 . Therefore we have only two independent parameters ϕ_5 and ϕ_6 :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_3 &= 1, \quad \phi_4 = 1 - \sqrt{2}\frac{k^2 + \epsilon^2}{\epsilon\lambda}\phi_5 + 2\sqrt{2}\frac{k}{\lambda}\phi_6, \\ \phi_1 &= \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\lambda} - \frac{k}{\epsilon}\frac{\epsilon^2 + 3k^2}{2\lambda^2}\phi_5 + 2\frac{2k^2 - \epsilon^2}{\lambda^2}\phi_6, \quad \phi_2 = \frac{k}{2\epsilon}\phi_5 - \phi_6 - \frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\lambda}. \end{aligned} \tag{5.7}$$

Thus, we can fix 2 independent solutions as follows

$$\phi_3 = 1, \phi_5 = 1, \phi_6 = 0, \phi_4 = \frac{\lambda\epsilon - \sqrt{2}(\epsilon^2 + k^2)}{\lambda\epsilon}, \phi_1 = \frac{(\sqrt{2}\lambda\epsilon - \epsilon^2 - 3k^2)k}{2\lambda^2\epsilon}, \phi_2 = \frac{(\lambda - \sqrt{2}\epsilon)k}{2\epsilon\lambda}; \tag{5.8}$$

$$\phi_3 = 1, \phi_5 = 0, \phi_6 = 1, \phi_4 = 2\sqrt{2}\frac{k}{\lambda}, \phi_1 = \frac{\lambda k + 2\sqrt{2}k^2 - \sqrt{2}\epsilon^2 + \sqrt{2}k^2}{\sqrt{2}\lambda^2}, \phi_2 = -\frac{k}{\sqrt{2}\lambda} - 1. \tag{5.9}$$

Because the above decompositions of 4 gauge solutions on 6 independent Ψ_i coincide for the variants *I* and *II*: results on gauge free constituents derived for the case *I* are also valid for the variant *II*.

6. Conclusions

We have developed the theory of the massless spin 2 particle in cylindrical coordinates. We have find six independent solutions. In order to eliminate the gauge degrees of freedom, we use the Pauli – Fierz approach, when the gauge

solutions for spin 2 field are constructed with the use of the four exact solutions for a massless spin 1 field. In the end, we have derived explicit form of two gauge-free solutions for massless spin 2 field, which do not contain gauge components, and contribute to energy-momentum tensor [25]. This analysis agrees with the results obtained for a spherically symmetric case for a massless spin 2 field, see the recent paper [31].

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